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1 MTAPGRS**S**P**L**E**P**L**L**E**T**W**E**D**P**S**V**P**P**G**E**Q**T**D**A**Y**L**T**L**T**S**R**M**T**G**E**E**C**K**E**V**I**A**E**I**E**K**N**L**S**R**L**Y**T**V**L 60
 61 **K**A**H**I**S**S**O**N**S**E**L**S**S**A**A**L**O**A**L**G**F**C**L**Y**N**F**R**I**T**S**L**S**E**A**N**I**Q**E**L**L**L**T**I**N**G**I**T**K**S**S**D**K**N**V**C**T**R**A**L** 120
 121 **W**V**I**S**K**O**T**F**P**A**E**L**V**S**K**M**V**S**S**I**D**S**L**E**V**I**L**S**K**G**E**I**H**S**A**V**V**D**F**E**A**L**N**V**I**I**S**H**W**F**L**H**C**R**L**I**E****Q**A 180
 181 **P**V**Q**M**G**E**E**S**V**R**W**A**K**L**V**I**P**L**V**V**H**S**A**O**K****V**H**L**R**G**A**T**A**L**E**M**G**M**P**L**L**L****Q**K**Q**E**I**A**L**I**T**E**H**L**M**T**T**K**L** 240
 241 **I**S**E**L**Q****L**L**F**K**N**K**N**E**T**Y**V**L**K**L**W**P**L**F**V**K**L**L**G**K**T**L**H**R**S**G**S**F**I**N**S**L**L****Q**L**E**E**L**G**H**R**S**G**T**P**M**I**K**K**I**A 300
 301 **F**I**A**W**K**S**L**I**D**N**F**A**L**N**P**D**I**I**S**A**K**R**L**K**L**L**M**Q**P**L**S**S**I**H**V**R**T**E**T**L**A**L**T**K**L**E**V**W**Y**L**L**M**R**L**G**P**Q**L 360
 361 **P**A**N**F**E****V**C**V**P**L**I**Q**S**T**I**S**V**S**I**P**S**P**Q**G**N**S**S**R**G**S**A**S**P**G**L**S**P**L**T**P**G**H**K**K**A**S**P**Y**G**S**P**R**E**N**L**S**S**N** 420
 421 **T**G**G**M**A**I**P**S**I**Q**L**L**G**L**E**M**M**L**H**F**L**L**G**P**E**V**L**S**F**A**K**Q**H**K**I**V**L**S**L**E**P**L**E**H**P**L**I**S**S**P**S**F**F**S**K**Y**A**H**T** 480
 481 **L**I**T**A**V**H**D**S**F**V**S**V**K****D**A**S**A**V**V**S**A**I**W**K**E**L**I**S**L**V**K**S**V**T**E**A**G**N**R**K**E**K**S**G**S**E**V**L**T**L**L**L**K**S**L**E**N**I** 540
 541 **V**K**S**E**V**F**P**V**S**K**T**L**V**L**M**E**I**T**V**K**L**P**P**K**V**L**G**S**P**A**Y**Q**V**A**N**M**D**I**L**N**G**T**P**A**L**F**L**I**Q**L**I**F**N**N**L**L**E**C 600
 601 **G**V**E**D**E**K**F**F**L**N**L**E**T**L**V**G**C**V**L**S**G**P**T**S**P**L**A**F**S**D**S**V**L**T**V**I**N**Q**N**A**K**Q**L**V**N**K**E**H**L**W**R**M**W**S**M**I**V**S**P**L 660
 661 **T**D**V**I**H**Q**T**N**E**V**N**Q**G**D**A**L**E**H**N**F**S**A**I**Y**G**A**L**T**L**P**I**N**H**I**F**S**A**Q**T**F**P**T**G**T**M**K**A**L**L**K**T**W**S**E**L**Y**R**A**F**T 720
 721 **P**C**A**S**L**V**A**T**A**E**E**N**I**C**C**E**E**L**S**K**I**M**C**S**L**E**D**E**V**L**S**D**L**L**F**L**D**R**I**S**H**I**I**V**M**V**D**C**I**D**F**S**P**Y**N**K**K**Y 780
 781 **Q**P**K**I**K**S**P**Q**R**S**S**D**W**S**R**K**K**E**P**L**G**K**L**A**S**L**F**K**L**I**V**K**V**I**D**F**H**T**L**S**L**K**E**T**F**S**D**T**L**L**A**I**G**N**S**I**S** 840
 841 **M**L**S**N**V**F**G**H**I**S**L**P**S**M**I**R**E**I**F**A**T**F**T**R**P**L**A**L**L**Y**E**N**S**K**L**D**E**A**P**K**V**Y**T**S**L**N**N**K**L**E**K**L**L**G**E**I**V**A**C**L 900
 901 **Q**F**S**Y**L**G**A**Y**D**S**E**L**L**H**L**S**L**L**C**V**I**F**L**H**K**N**K**Q**I**R**K**Q**S**A**L**L**W**N**A**T**F**A**K**A**T**A**L**V**Y**P**E**E**L**K**P**I**L**R 960
 961 **Q**A**K**Q**K**I**L**L**L**L**P**G**L**E**N**V**E**M**M**D**E**S**S**E**P**Y**S**E**S**T**E**N**S**Q**L**N**V**K**I**S**G**M**E**R**K**S**S**G**H**R**D**S**I**L**A**H**T**K**D**K 1020
 1021 **K**K**K**V**K**L**S**A**K**L**K**L**E**S**S**S**P**K**I**K**S**G**K**L**L**E**E**E**K**S**T**D**F**V**F**I**P**P**E**G**K**E**T**K**A**R**V**L**T**E**H**Q**K**E**V**L**K**T**K**R 1080
 1081 **C**D**I**P**A**L**Y**N**N**L**D**A**S**Q**D**T**L**F**S**A**Q**F**S**Q**E**E**S**M**E**S**L**T**L**T**E**K**P**K**D**A**K**I**K**E**E**Q**M**E**S**T**I**F**I**H**Q**D**A**P 1140
 1141 **E**N**C**G**I**D**E**H**S**E**N**A**S**L**N**P**C**G**G**S**V**A**E**T**N**P**E**L**I**T**G**F**D**A**R**K**E**V**L**I**S**S**K**I**L**S**A**E**S**S**S**T**E**T**S**V**S** 1200
 1201 **S**S**S**V**S**N**A**T**F**S**G**T**P**P**Q**P**T**S**R**R**Q**T**F**I**L**E**K**F**D**G**S**E**T**R**P**F**S**P**S**P**L**N**N**I**S**S**T**V**T**V**R**N**N**O**D**N**T**T**N** 1260
 1261 **T**D**M**P**P**K**A**R**K**R**E**V**T**N**S**K**S**D**E**N**L**A**N**A**G**K**K**S**S**R**F**W**S**K**A**E**Q**S**V**T**K**K**S**K**P**S**L**T**S**E**Q**E**H**S**S**E**N**N 1320
 1321 **S**P**D**L**L**S**P**T**E**H**V**S**E**N**D**D**H**P**S**E**A**T**L**E**H**K**D**G**D**P**K**P**A**V**E**N**A**S**L**E**D**L**T**E**E**K**N**V**G**I**N**E**S**K**E**S**T**A 1380
 1381 **S**V**V**A**R**E**T**Q**I**V**N**E**D**S**O**A**A**A**L**A**P**N**P**K**L**L**R**R**S**S**F**R**R**S**E**A**V**D**S**C**S**D**S**O**E**R**E**S**G**Q**K**K**E**R**R**K**E**E**E** 1440
 1441 **K**I**I**S**K**S**P**L**R**I**K**D**K**L**D**L**D**K**L**T**D**E**S**P**I**Q**E**N**L**T**E**K**G**N**T**L**P**E**R**T**S**G**E**P**S**V**N**A**E**I**D**Q**N**R**R**K**P**D**L** 1500
 1501 **E**N**V**S**S**E**G**G**G**T**L**D**N**L**D**K**S**S**E**K**P**L**R**G**R**T**R**Y**Q**T**F**R**A**S**Q**G**L**I**S**A**V**E**N**S**E**S**D**S**S**E**A**K**E**E**V**S**R**K**K** 1560
 1561 **R**S**G**K**W**K**N**R**S**S**D**S**V**D**I**E**E**Q**E**K**K**A**E**E**V**M**K**T**A**N**Q**T**L**D**G**Q**A**V**P**D**V**D**V**N**A**A**A**Q**V**C**E**K**S**T**N**N**N**R 1620
 1621 **V**I**L**Q**D**S**A**G**P**A**D**S**L**Q**A**P**P**K**G**E**E**K**S**K**I**N**K**C**V**D**S**S**F**V**S**L**P**V**P**E**S**N**L**R**R**N**A**S**K**R**L**L**Y**K**Q**D**N**D**S** 1680
 1681 **N**V**R**V**S**D**S**S**L**S**P**E**K**F**T**Q**V**E**Q**H**K**R**S**R**R**V**R**S**K**S**C**D**C**C**G**E**K**S**Q**S**Q**E**K**S**F**I**G**L**K**N**T**E**S**Y**A**I**K**S 1740
 1741 **V**E**K**K**K**T**D**L**Q**V**P**E**T**A**P**E**T**R**E**A**R**D**H**A**E**T**K**L**A**G**E**E**P**L**V**N**F**H**V**G**L**K**E**B**N**C**T**T**G**D**S**V**K**S**E**A**E**L**Q**E 1800
 1801 **A**S**L**P**P**E**I**V**T**V**K**E**K**T**Y**D**T**D**A**S**E**A**V**S**E**L**Q**G**P**C**S**E**N**H**S**P**A**E**D**P**L**S**E**C**K**D**I**S**Q**K**Q**L**S**E**N**G**E**L**D** 1860
 1861 **I**S**D**V**G**K**A**C**K**V**I**A**G**S**S**P**E**G**V**E**T**M**E**L**N**V**R**N**D**A**F**V**A**A**D**S**E**K**S**T**Q**M**D**V**S**V**D**V**A**T**E**D**N**K**K**D**E**C**E** 1920
 1921 **A**V**T**T**E**V**N**V**E**G**V**A**T**E**D**F**N**S**G**M**D**L**S**D**T**P**I**P**V**S**K**D**V**E**T**E**H**A**A**S**G**E**I**E**G**E**S**N**E**S**D**S**G**S**C**E**E**M**N**K 1980
 1981 **E**M**G**S**H**K**A**Q**M**S**T**E**I**D**S**A**R**V**K**E**T**D**I**L**A**S**A**S**K**S**E**E**A**L**I**G**R**L**D**V**N**T**Q**S**F**V**S**D**I**E**M**S**S**G**B**R**T**V**N**C 2040
 2041 **K**T**E**T**S**I**E**L**N**K**L**D**E**A**K**L**S**G**N**E**A**T**V**G**N**D**T**L**Q**E**V**G**F**T**S**E**K**V**E**K**L**P**Q**C**L**L**V**Q**V**A**S**E**L**G**A**S**N**T**T** 2100
 2101 **S**P**E**K**L**E**L**D**S**F**G**S**V**N**E**S**P**S**G**M**Q**A**R**C**V**W**S**P**L**A**S**P**S**T**S**I**I**K**R**G**L**R**S**Q**E**D**E**I**S**P**V**N**K**L**R**V**S** 2160
 2161 **F**A**D**P**I**Y**Q**A**G**L**A**D**D**I**D**R**R**C**S**V**V**R**S**H**S**N**S**S**P**I**I**K**S**V**K**T**S**P**T**S**H**S**K**H**N**T**S**A**K**G**F**L**S**P**G**S**Q**S 2220
 2221 **S**K**F**K**S**P**K**K**L**I**T**E**M**A**Q**E**S**M**L**S**P**T**E**S**V**Y**P**A**L**V**N**C**A**A**S**V**D**I**L**P**Q**I**T**S**N**M**A**R**G**L**G**Q**L**I**R**A**K** 2280
 2281 **N**I**K**T**I**G**D**L**S**T**L**T**A**S**E**I**K**L**P**L**I**R**S**P**K**V**N**V**K**K**A**L**R**V**Y**H**E**Q**M**K**S**R**G**L**E**E**I**P**I**F**D**I**S**E**K**A**V**N 2340
 2341 **G**V**E**S**R**T**V**S**T**D**E**B**F**F**A**S**D**L**E**P**V**T**L**D**T**P**L**S**K**N**L**V**A**Q**I**S**A**L**A**L**Q**L**D**S**E**D**L**Y**S**T**G**S**L**F**E**M**H** 2400
 2401 **E**K**L**G**T**M**A**N**S**I**I**R**N**L**Q**S**R**M**R**S**P**A**H**E**N**S 2426

show legend ?

- Complete mods:** i. Carbamidomethyl@C, Label:+6 Da@R, Label:+6 Da@K
- Potential mods:** i. Phospho@S, Phospho@T, Phospho@Y
ii. Oxidation@M, Oxidation@W, Deamidated@N, Deamidated@Q
iii. Dioxidation@M, Dioxidation@W
- Protein-specific PTMs:** i. Phospho@S, Acetyl@K
- N-terminal:** i. Ammonia-loss@Q, Ammonia-loss@C, Dehydrated@E (peptide)
ii. ragged, Acetyl (protein)

Identified Peptides

spectrum	log(e)	log(l)	m+h	delta	ζ	sequence	n
36415.1	-9.8	4.06	3347.662	1.001	2/2	apgr ⁷ SPLELLETW EDPSVPPGEQ TDAYLTLTSR ³⁶ mtge	(748)
36463.1	-9.7	3.80	3347.6625	-0.0040	2/2	apgr ⁷ SPLELLETW EDPSVPPGEQ TDAYLTLTSR ³⁶ mtge	(748)
36466.1	-7.5	3.87	3347.662	-0.013	2/2	apgr ⁷ SPLELLETW EDPSVPPGEQ TDAYLTLTSR ³⁶ mtge	(748)
36555.1	-7.3	3.70	3347.6625	-0.0035	3/3	apgr ⁷ SPLELLETW EDPSVPPGEQ TDAYLTLTSR ³⁶ mtge	(748)
36364.1	-7.2	4.13	3347.662	0.989	2/2	apgr ⁷ SPLELLETW EDPSVPPGEQ TDAYLTLTSR ³⁶ mtge	(748)

	model	homologues	context	group	gel	chip	peptide	table	details	go	path	doms	savs	mh	ζ	XML
33198.1	-6.0	3.99	1896.9831	-0.0001	2/2	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP DILCSAK ³²²	rIkI					(20600)			
33061.1	-4.1	4.56	1896.9831	-0.0000	3/3	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP DILCSAK ³²²	rIkI					(20600)			
34295.1	-3.6	3.69	1897.9671	0.0042	2/2	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP DILCSAK ³²²	rIkI					(20600)			
34298.1	-3.1	3.67	1897.9671	0.0053	2/2	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP DILCSAK ³²²	rIkI					(20600)			
33051.1	-2.7	4.58	1896.9831	0.0003	3/3	iawk ³⁰⁶	SLIDNFALNP DILCSAK ³²²	rIkI					(20600)			
21248.1	-11.8	4.25	1399.8185	0.0006	2/3	krIk ³²⁶	LLMQPLSSIH VR ³³⁷	tetI					(13901)			
21259.1	-11.5	4.34	1399.8185	-0.0014	2/3	krIk ³²⁶	LLMQPLSSIH VR ³³⁷	tetI					(13901)			
17907.1	-9.9	4.62	1415.8135	-0.0015	2/3	krIk ³²⁶	LLMQPLSSIH VR ³³⁷	tetI					(13901)			
17896.1	-9.6	4.53	1415.8135	-0.0016	2/3	krIk ³²⁶	LLMQPLSSIH VR ³³⁷	tetI					(13901)			
17875.1	-6.4	5.08	1415.8135	-0.0033	3/3	krIk ³²⁶	LLMQPLSSIH VR ³³⁷	tetI					(13901)			
18061.1	-5.8	4.83	1415.8135	-0.0016	3/3	krIk ³²⁶	LLMQPLSSIH VR ³³⁷	tetI					(13901)			
17864.1	-4.4	4.90	1415.8135	-0.0028	3/3	krIk ³²⁶	LLMQPLSSIH VR ³³⁷	tetI					(13901)			
18072.1	-2.6	4.74	1415.8135	-0.0016	3/3	krIk ³²⁶	LLMQPLSSIH VR ³³⁷	tetI					(13901)			
34561.1	-4.7	4.16	1430.7596	0.0004	2/2	altk ³⁴⁶	LEVWYLLMR ³⁵⁵	Igpq					(192)			
34565.1	-3.4	4.23	1430.7596	0.0008	2/2	altk ³⁴⁶	LEVWYLLMR ³⁵⁵	Igpq					(192)			
38474.1	-5.5	2.72	3405.736	0.999	2/2	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GN ³⁸⁷	ssrg					(76)			
38435.1	-5.5	3.34	3405.7359	-0.0020	3/2	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GN ³⁸⁷	ssrg					(76)			
38515.1	-5.5	3.41	3405.736	0.990	3/2	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GN ³⁸⁷	ssrg					(76)			
38445.1	-4.4	3.51	3405.7359	-0.0020	3/2	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GN ³⁸⁷	ssrg					(76)			
36044.1	-15.0	4.43	3741.9212	0.0027	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas					(560)			
35943.1	-6.4	3.36	3741.921	1.002	2/2	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas					(560)			
36091.1	-5.9	3.06	3742.905	0.018	2/2	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas					(560)			
36011.1	-5.6	3.70	3743.889	2.045	2/2	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas					(560)			
37035.1	-5.1	3.14	3742.9052	-0.0042	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas					(560)			
36056.1	-5.0	4.50	3741.9212	0.0020	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas					(560)			
37705.1	-4.3	2.78	3822.872	1.019	2/2	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas					(560)			
37664.1	-3.9	3.41	3821.8875	0.0099	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas					(560)			
37664.2	-3.9	3.41	3821.8875	0.0099	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas					(560)			
36100.1	-3.4	3.59	3743.889	2.047	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas					(560)			
35885.1	-3.2	3.38	3742.905	0.027	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas					(560)			
36129.1	-2.9	3.23	3742.905	0.037	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas					(560)			
37020.1	-2.8	3.22	3743.889	1.023	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas					(560)			
36087.1	-2.8	3.41	3742.905	0.026	2/2	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas					(560)			
36085.1	-2.8	3.85	3743.889	2.041	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas					(560)			
35980.1	-2.6	3.42	3741.9212	0.0007	2/2	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas					(560)			
37790.1	-2.6	3.37	3822.872	0.016	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas					(560)			
35977.1	-2.5	3.53	3741.9212	-0.0044	2/2	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas					(560)			
36280.1	-2.3	3.22	3743.889	0.011	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas					(560)			
35937.1	-2.2	3.82	3743.889	2.048	3/3	llmr ³⁵⁶	LGPQLPANFE QVCVPLIQST ISVDSIPSPQ GNSSR ³⁹⁰	gsas					(560)			
11771.1	-6.8	4.58	1411.7635	-0.0010	2/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp					(3621)			
11757.1	-6.2	4.27	1411.7635	-0.0015	2/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp					(3621)			
11763.1	-4.8	4.42	1411.7635	-0.0007	2/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp					(3621)			
14686.1	-4.7	3.92	1491.7299	0.0019	2/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp					(3621)			
18165.1	-3.9	3.70	1571.6962	-0.0017	2/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp					(3621)			
15308.1	-3.8	3.89	1491.7299	-0.0023	2/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp					(3621)			
18175.1	-3.5	3.75	1571.6962	0.0015	2/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp					(3621)			
15319.1	-3.3	3.94	1491.7299	-0.0001	2/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp					(3621)			
18155.1	-2.8	3.67	1571.6962	0.0025	2/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp					(3621)			
11748.1	-2.5	4.78	1411.7635	-0.0017	3/3	nssr ³⁹¹	GSASPLSPL TPGHK ⁴⁰⁵	gasp					(3621)			
5749.1	-4.5	4.58	897.4520	-0.0011	2/2	pghk ⁴⁰⁶	GASPYGSPR ⁴¹⁴	gnls					(535)			

	model	homologues	context	group	gel	chip	peptide	table	details	go	path	doms	savs	mh	ζ	XML
34234.2	-4.5	3.59	3746.7970	0.0019	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
34234.3	-4.5	3.59	3746.7970	0.0019	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
34272.1	-4.2	3.60	3746.7970	-0.0008	2/2	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
34272.2	-4.2	3.60	3746.7970	-0.0008	2/2	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
34272.3	-4.2	3.60	3746.7970	-0.0008	2/2	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
37135.1	-3.6	3.63	3826.7633	-0.0030	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
37135.2	-3.6	3.63	3826.7633	-0.0030	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
37135.3	-3.6	3.63	3826.7633	-0.0030	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
37135.4	-3.6	3.63	3826.7633	-0.0030	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
39704.1	-3.6	3.07	3906.730	1.001	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
39704.2	-3.6	3.07	3906.730	1.001	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
37910.1	-3.5	3.28	3810.768	0.019	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
37910.2	-3.5	3.28	3810.768	0.019	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
37910.3	-3.5	3.28	3810.768	0.019	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
37910.4	-3.5	3.28	3810.768	0.019	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
34379.1	-3.5	3.49	3746.7970	-0.0032	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
35263.1	-3.2	3.15	3730.8021	0.0026	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
35263.2	-3.2	3.15	3730.8021	0.0026	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
37003.1	-3.0	3.49	3826.7633	-0.0023	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
37003.2	-3.0	3.49	3826.7633	-0.0023	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
36997.1	-3.0	3.45	3826.7633	0.0069	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
36997.2	-3.0	3.45	3826.7633	0.0069	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
34222.1	-2.8	3.36	3746.797	-0.024	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
34222.2	-2.8	3.36	3746.797	-0.024	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
34222.3	-2.8	3.36	3746.797	-0.024	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
35903.1	-2.7	3.19	3731.786	0.018	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
37904.1	-2.5	3.37	3810.7684	-0.0023	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
37904.2	-2.5	3.37	3810.7684	-0.0023	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
34386.1	-2.5	3.40	3746.7970	-0.0006	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
36980.1	-2.4	3.24	3826.763	1.005	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
36980.2	-2.4	3.24	3826.763	1.005	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
36980.3	-2.4	3.24	3826.763	1.005	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
36980.4	-2.4	3.24	3826.763	1.005	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
35896.1	-2.0	3.05	3731.786	0.015	3/3	akqk ⁹⁶⁶	ILLLLPLEN VEMIMDESSEP YSESTENSQI NVK	998	isgm				(5376)			
2646.1	-2.7	3.81	1052.6250	-0.0022	3/4	ssgk ¹⁰¹⁰	DSILAHTK ¹⁰¹⁸ dkkk						(30)			
6441.1	-6.5	5.37	890.5037	-0.0011	2/3	sgkr ¹⁰¹¹	DSILAHTK ¹⁰¹⁸ dkkk						(792)			
6452.1	-6.3	5.51	890.5037	-0.0011	2/3	sgkr ¹⁰¹¹	DSILAHTK ¹⁰¹⁸ dkkk						(792)			
5696.1	-5.1	4.16	1139.6458	-0.0012	2/4	sgkr ¹⁰¹¹	DSILAHTK ¹⁰²⁰ kkkv						(2)			
5672.1	-3.0	4.11	1139.6458	-0.0005	2/4	sgkr ¹⁰¹¹	DSILAHTK ¹⁰²⁰ kkkv						(2)			
5687.1	-2.4	4.12	1139.6458	-0.0011	2/4	sgkr ¹⁰¹¹	DSILAHTK ¹⁰²⁰ kkkv						(2)			
7025.1	-4.6	4.45	1080.5739	-0.0009	2/3	lsak ¹⁰³⁰	LKLESSPK ¹⁰³⁸ iks						(172)			
7046.1	-4.1	4.47	1080.5739	-0.0009	2/3	lsak ¹⁰³⁰	LKLESSPK ¹⁰³⁸ iks						(172)			
5528.1	-2.7	4.80	1000.6076	-0.0006	2/3	lsak ¹⁰³⁰	LKLESSPK ¹⁰³⁸ iks						(172)			
5517.1	-2.2	4.59	1000.6076	-0.0005	2/3	lsak ¹⁰³⁰	LKLESSPK ¹⁰³⁸ iks						(172)			
4234.1	-6.0	4.10	1044.5974	-0.0008	2/3	pkik ¹⁰⁴¹	SGKLEEEK ¹⁰⁴⁹ stf						(6)			
4225.1	-4.8	4.02	1044.5974	-0.0009	2/3	pkik ¹⁰⁴¹	SGKLEEEK ¹⁰⁴⁹ stf						(6)			
24690.1	-4.8	3.92	2448.2444	-0.0016	3/4	pkik ¹⁰⁴¹	SGKLEEEKS ¹⁰⁶¹ etka						(30)			
24712.1	-4.3	3.82	2448.2444	-0.0016	3/4	pkik ¹⁰⁴¹	SGKLEEEKS ¹⁰⁶¹ etka						(30)			
5164.1	-3.9	5.05	766.4288	-0.0002	2/2	ksgk ¹⁰⁴⁴	LLEEEK ¹⁰⁴⁹ stf						(292)			
5154.1	-3.2	4.84	766.4288	-0.0000	2/2	ksgk ¹⁰⁴⁴	LLEEEK ¹⁰⁴⁹ stf						(292)			

model	homologues	context	group	gel	chip	peptide	table	details	go	path	doms	savs	mh	ζ	XML
7745.1	-5.3	3.65	1595.7061	-0.0018	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
7327.1	-5.3	3.55	1595.7061	0.0006	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
8555.1	-5.2	3.66	1595.7061	0.0002	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
8160.1	-5.2	3.65	1595.7061	-0.0020	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
8992.1	-5.1	3.70	1595.7061	0.0009	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
9404.1	-5.0	3.61	1595.7061	0.0015	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
8982.1	-5.0	3.67	1595.7061	-0.0014	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
7534.1	-4.9	3.58	1595.7061	-0.0029	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
7557.1	-4.9	3.60	1595.7061	-0.0020	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
6315.1	-4.8	3.50	1612.6851	-0.0001	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
9790.1	-4.4	3.56	1595.7061	-0.0011	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
5865.1	-4.4	3.44	1612.6851	0.0004	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
6348.1	-4.4	3.49	1612.6851	0.0000	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
8356.1	-4.4	3.71	1595.7061	-0.0014	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
5883.1	-4.4	3.52	1612.6851	-0.0041	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
9601.1	-4.3	3.62	1595.7061	-0.0009	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
9587.1	-4.2	3.63	1595.7061	0.0006	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
9812.1	-4.0	3.57	1595.7061	-0.0048	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
6355.1	-3.9	3.44	1612.6851	-0.0019	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
6615.1	-3.8	3.55	1612.6851	-0.0028	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
10017.1	-3.8	3.52	1595.7061	0.0006	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
9576.1	-3.7	3.58	1595.7061	0.0028	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
8774.1	-3.7	3.67	1595.7061	-0.0022	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
9820.1	-3.7	3.51	1595.7061	-0.0024	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
7751.1	-3.5	3.58	1595.7061	-0.0013	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
10236.1	-3.4	3.40	1595.7061	-0.0026	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
9382.1	-2.7	3.60	1595.7061	-0.0003	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
10224.1	-2.6	3.41	1595.7061	-0.0049	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
6070.1	-2.6	3.41	1612.6851	-0.0005	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
10829.1	-2.5	3.46	1595.7061	-0.0021	2/2	vtvr ¹²⁵³	NNQDNTTNTD MPPK	¹²⁶⁶ arkr							(3095)
7934.1	-8.3	3.69	1775.8809	-0.0039	2/3	arkr ¹²⁷¹	EVTNSKSDSE NLANAGK	¹²⁸⁷ kssr							(119)
7926.1	-4.6	4.38	1775.8809	-0.0005	3/3	arkr ¹²⁷¹	EVTNSKSDSE NLANAGK	¹²⁸⁷ kssr							(119)
9327.1	-4.4	3.50	1776.8649	0.0037	2/3	arkr ¹²⁷¹	EVTNSKSDSE NLANAGK	¹²⁸⁷ kssr							(119)
9330.1	-3.6	4.11	1776.8649	-0.0012	3/3	arkr ¹²⁷¹	EVTNSKSDSE NLANAGK	¹²⁸⁷ kssr							(119)
7903.1	-3.3	4.13	1775.8809	-0.0016	3/3	arkr ¹²⁷¹	EVTNSKSDSE NLANAGK	¹²⁸⁷ kssr							(119)
7953.1	-3.3	3.51	1775.8809	-0.0012	2/3	arkr ¹²⁷¹	EVTNSKSDSE NLANAGK	¹²⁸⁷ kssr							(119)
7964.1	-2.8	3.48	1775.8809	0.0000	2/3	arkr ¹²⁷¹	EVTNSKSDSE NLANAGK	¹²⁸⁷ kssr							(119)
9337.1	-2.5	3.50	1776.8649	-0.0017	2/3	arkr ¹²⁷¹	EVTNSKSDSE NLANAGK	¹²⁸⁷ kssr							(119)
9315.1	-2.1	3.49	1776.8649	0.0016	2/3	arkr ¹²⁷¹	EVTNSKSDSE NLANAGK	¹²⁸⁷ kssr							(119)
6324.1	-2.1	3.88	1909.9960	-0.0012	3/4	arkr ¹²⁷¹	EVTNSKSDSE NLANAGKK	¹²⁸⁸ ssrr							(44)
5737.1	-8.0	4.64	1111.5321	-0.0011	2/2	tnsk ¹²⁷⁷	SDSENLANAGK	¹²⁸⁷ kssr							(852)
5726.1	-7.3	4.37	1111.5321	-0.0007	2/2	tnsk ¹²⁷⁷	SDSENLANAGK	¹²⁸⁷ kssr							(852)
5927.1	-6.5	3.84	1111.5321	0.0000	2/2	tnsk ¹²⁷⁷	SDSENLANAGK	¹²⁸⁷ kssr							(852)
5396.1	-4.7	3.83	1112.5161	-0.0005	2/2	tnsk ¹²⁷⁷	SDSENLANAGK	¹²⁸⁷ kssr							(852)
3040.1	-9.1	3.99	1245.6472	0.0003	2/3	tnsk ¹²⁷⁷	SDSENLANAGKK	¹²⁸⁸ ssrr							(426)
3037.1	-4.4	3.96	1245.6472	0.0010	2/3	tnsk ¹²⁷⁷	SDSENLANAGKK	¹²⁸⁸ ssrr							(426)
3233.1	-3.1	3.52	1245.6472	-0.0034	2/3	tnsk ¹²⁷⁷	SDSENLANAGKK	¹²⁸⁸ ssrr							(426)
3452.1	-3.0	3.57	1246.6312	-0.0025	2/3	tnsk ¹²⁷⁷	SDSENLANAGKK	¹²⁸⁸ ssrr							(426)
3242.1	-3.0	3.47	1245.6472	-0.0017	2/3	tnsk ¹²⁷⁷	SDSENLANAGKK	¹²⁸⁸ ssrr							(426)
3440.1	-2.9	3.46	1246.6312	-0.0010	2/3	tnsk ¹²⁷⁷	SDSENLANAGKK	¹²⁸⁸ ssrr							(426)

	model	homologues	context	group	gel	chip	peptide	table	details	go	path	doms	savs	mh	ζ	XML
13508.1	-12.1	3.94	3165.2322	-0.0019	3/3	pvs ^{k1952}	DVTEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC ^{EEMNK}	1980	emgs				(4657)			
15665.1	-11.6	3.93	3133.2424	-0.0002	3/3	pvs ^{k1952}	DVTEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC ^{EEMNK}	1980	emgs				(4657)			
17090.1	-10.1	3.59	3213.2087	-0.0018	3/3	pvs ^{k1952}	DVTEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC ^{EEMNK}	1980	emgs				(4657)			
14426.1	-8.9	3.43	3150.2213	0.0090	3/3	pvs ^{k1952}	DVTEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC ^{EEMNK}	1980	emgs				(4657)			
15184.1	-8.4	3.75	3229.2036	-0.0010	3/3	pvs ^{k1952}	DVTEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC ^{EEMNK}	1980	emgs				(4657)			
14151.1	-7.7	3.47	3149.2373	-0.0045	3/3	pvs ^{k1952}	DVTEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC ^{EEMNK}	1980	emgs				(4657)			
14177.1	-7.3	3.57	3149.2373	0.0002	3/3	pvs ^{k1952}	DVTEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC ^{EEMNK}	1980	emgs				(4657)			
17076.1	-6.5	3.65	3213.2087	-0.0015	3/3	pvs ^{k1952}	DVTEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC ^{EEMNK}	1980	emgs				(4657)			
13497.1	-6.3	3.89	3165.2322	-0.0034	3/3	pvs ^{k1952}	DVTEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC ^{EEMNK}	1980	emgs				(4657)			
15192.1	-6.2	3.79	3229.2036	-0.0010	3/3	pvs ^{k1952}	DVTEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC ^{EEMNK}	1980	emgs				(4657)			
17065.1	-5.7	3.60	3213.2087	-0.0018	3/3	pvs ^{k1952}	DVTEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC ^{EEMNK}	1980	emgs				(4657)			
15076.1	-5.2	3.46	3149.2373	-0.0042	3/3	pvs ^{k1952}	DVTEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC ^{EEMNK}	1980	emgs				(4657)			
15369.1	-5.0	3.71	3229.204	0.014	3/3	pvs ^{k1952}	DVTEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC ^{EEMNK}	1980	emgs				(4657)			
16703.1	-4.6	3.69	3309.1700	-0.0004	3/3	pvs ^{k1952}	DVTEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC ^{EEMNK}	1980	emgs				(4657)			
15380.1	-4.1	3.71	3229.2036	-0.0039	3/3	pvs ^{k1952}	DVTEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC ^{EEMNK}	1980	emgs				(4657)			
15175.1	-3.2	3.69	3229.2036	-0.0091	3/3	pvs ^{k1952}	DVTEHAASG EIEGESNESD SGSC ^{EEMNK}	1980	emgs				(4657)			
6661.1	-10.1	5.18	1230.5726	-0.0010	2/2	gsh ^{k1987}	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vkct				(3385)			
10792.1	-8.1	4.49	1214.5777	-0.0012	2/2	gsh ^{k1987}	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vkct				(3385)			
6463.1	-7.9	4.44	1230.5726	-0.0018	2/2	gsh ^{k1987}	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vkct				(3385)			
10783.1	-7.8	4.25	1214.5777	-0.0001	2/2	gsh ^{k1987}	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vkct				(3385)			
6650.1	-7.2	5.34	1230.5726	-0.0014	2/2	gsh ^{k1987}	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vkct				(3385)			
6460.1	-6.0	4.32	1230.5726	-0.0034	2/2	gsh ^{k1987}	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vkct				(3385)			
7136.1	-5.8	3.87	1246.5675	-0.0023	2/2	gsh ^{k1987}	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vkct				(3385)			
7119.1	-5.4	3.78	1246.5675	-0.0033	2/2	gsh ^{k1987}	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vkct				(3385)			
10983.1	-5.1	3.68	1214.5777	0.0024	2/2	gsh ^{k1987}	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vkct				(3385)			
11005.1	-4.5	3.68	1214.5777	0.0002	2/2	gsh ^{k1987}	AQMSTEIDSA R	1997	vkct				(3385)			
12343.1	-11.0	4.05	1273.7401	-0.0003	2/3	dsar ¹⁹⁹⁸	VKETDILASA SK	2009	seea				(1025)			
12353.1	-10.4	4.38	1273.7401	-0.0017	2/3	dsar ¹⁹⁹⁸	VKETDILASA SK	2009	seea				(1025)			
12364.1	-4.6	4.90	1273.7401	-0.0018	3/3	dsar ¹⁹⁹⁸	VKETDILASA SK	2009	seea				(1025)			
12375.1	-3.1	5.10	1273.7401	-0.0014	3/3	dsar ¹⁹⁹⁸	VKETDILASA SK	2009	seea				(1025)			
23818.1	-14.7	4.24	2135.2053	-0.0029	3/4	dsar ¹⁹⁹⁸	VKETDILASA SKSEALIGR	2017	ldvn				(86)			
23808.1	-9.9	4.09	2135.2053	-0.0044	3/4	dsar ¹⁹⁹⁸	VKETDILASA SKSEALIGR	2017	ldvn				(86)			
11815.1	-4.3	4.95	1040.5566	-0.0010	2/2	arvk ²⁰⁰⁰	ETDILASASK	2009	seea				(605)			
11806.1	-3.8	4.73	1040.5566	-0.0002	2/2	arvk ²⁰⁰⁰	ETDILASASK	2009	seea				(605)			
24895.1	-15.0	4.46	1902.0217	-0.0009	2/3	arvk ²⁰⁰⁰	ETDILASASKSEALIGR	2017	ldvn				(63)			
24867.1	-15.0	4.29	1902.0217	-0.0004	2/3	arvk ²⁰⁰⁰	ETDILASASKSEALIGR	2017	ldvn				(63)			
24884.1	-5.7	4.91	1902.0217	-0.0016	3/3	arvk ²⁰⁰⁰	ETDILASASKSEALIGR	2017	ldvn				(63)			
24952.1	-3.5	4.39	1902.0217	-0.0003	3/3	arvk ²⁰⁰⁰	ETDILASASKSEALIGR	2017	ldvn				(63)			
24904.1	-2.2	4.22	1902.0217	-0.0009	2/3	arvk ²⁰⁰⁰	ETDILASASKSEALIGR	2017	ldvn				(63)			
10505.1	-5.1	5.56	880.4830	-0.0005	2/2	sask ²⁰¹⁰	SEALIGR	2017	ldvn				(352)			
10516.1	-2.7	5.59	880.4830	-0.0003	2/2	sask ²⁰¹⁰	SEALIGR	2017	ldvn				(352)			
32793.1	-11.2	4.32	2997.4508	0.0036	3/3	sask ²⁰¹⁰	SEALIGRLD VNTQSFVSDI EMSSGER	2036	tvnc				(76)			
32796.1	-10.8	4.27	2997.4508	0.0001	3/3	sask ²⁰¹⁰	SEALIGRLD VNTQSFVSDI EMSSGER	2036	tvnc				(76)			
32535.1	-8.9	3.85	2997.4508	-0.0011	3/3	sask ²⁰¹⁰	SEALIGRLD VNTQSFVSDI EMSSGER	2036	tvnc				(76)			
33163.1	-7.2	4.03	2981.456	0.018	3/3	sask ²⁰¹⁰	SEALIGRLD VNTQSFVSDI EMSSGER	2036	tvnc				(76)			
33175.1	-5.3	3.93	2981.456	0.023	3/3	sask ²⁰¹⁰	SEALIGRLD VNTQSFVSDI EMSSGER	2036	tvnc				(76)			
32528.1	-5.2	3.77	2997.4508	-0.0048	3/3	sask ²⁰¹⁰	SEALIGRLD VNTQSFVSDI EMSSGER	2036	tvnc				(76)			
33268.1	-4.6	3.63	2981.4559	-0.0075	3/3	sask ²⁰¹⁰	SEALIGRLD VNTQSFVSDI EMSSGER	2036	tvnc				(76)			
33282.1	-3.4	3.53	2981.456	0.999	3/3	sask ²⁰¹⁰	SEALIGRLD VNTQSFVSDI EMSSGER	2036	tvnc				(76)			
33287.1	-3.1	3.60	2982.440	0.024	3/3	sask ²⁰¹⁰	SEALIGRLD VNTQSFVSDI EMSSGER	2036	tvnc				(76)			

3477.1	-2.1	4.19	838.4360	-0.0011	2/2	isek ²³³⁸	AVNGVESR ²³⁴⁵	tvst	(116)
31748.1	-7.2	4.08	2775.4337	0.0011	3/3	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEERFA	SDLIEPVTLD TPLSK ²³⁷⁰	nlva (1156)
31551.1	-6.9	3.53	2775.434	-0.011	2/3	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEERFA	SDLIEPVTLD TPLSK ²³⁷⁰	nlva (1156)
31489.1	-5.9	3.86	2775.4337	0.0057	3/3	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEERFA	SDLIEPVTLD TPLSK ²³⁷⁰	nlva (1156)
31744.1	-4.8	4.10	2775.4337	-0.0042	3/3	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEERFA	SDLIEPVTLD TPLSK ²³⁷⁰	nlva (1156)
31557.1	-3.7	3.57	2775.4337	-0.0006	2/3	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEERFA	SDLIEPVTLD TPLSK ²³⁷⁰	nlva (1156)
31486.1	-3.6	3.75	2775.4337	-0.0053	3/3	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEERFA	SDLIEPVTLD TPLSK ²³⁷⁰	nlva (1156)
31563.1	-2.4	3.56	2775.4337	-0.0006	2/3	vesr ²³⁴⁶	TVSTDEERFA	SDLIEPVTLD TPLSK ²³⁷⁰	nlva (1156)
29995.1	-10.9	4.43	1852.0045	-0.0006	2/2	deer ²³⁵⁴	FASDLIEPVT	LDTPLSK ²³⁷⁰	nlva (5251)
29794.1	-10.1	4.39	1852.0045	0.0009	2/2	deer ²³⁵⁴	FASDLIEPVT	LDTPLSK ²³⁷⁰	nlva (5251)
29984.1	-8.0	4.70	1852.0045	-0.0008	2/2	deer ²³⁵⁴	FASDLIEPVT	LDTPLSK ²³⁷⁰	nlva (5251)
29783.1	-6.5	4.01	1852.0045	0.0009	2/2	deer ²³⁵⁴	FASDLIEPVT	LDTPLSK ²³⁷⁰	nlva (5251)
29877.1	-5.1	4.52	1852.0045	-0.0012	3/3	deer ²³⁵⁴	FASDLIEPVT	LDTPLSK ²³⁷⁰	nlva (5251)
29867.1	-5.0	4.48	1852.0045	-0.0015	3/3	deer ²³⁵⁴	FASDLIEPVT	LDTPLSK ²³⁷⁰	nlva (5251)
30189.1	-4.4	3.72	1852.005	1.004	2/2	deer ²³⁵⁴	FASDLIEPVT	LDTPLSK ²³⁷⁰	nlva (5251)
30205.1	-3.4	3.66	1852.0045	-0.0021	2/2	deer ²³⁵⁴	FASDLIEPVT	LDTPLSK ²³⁷⁰	nlva (5251)
30225.1	-2.1	3.58	1852.0045	-0.0038	2/2	deer ²³⁵⁴	FASDLIEPVT	LDTPLSK ²³⁷⁰	nlva (5251)
39082.1	-2.6	3.17	3636.772	0.016	3/3	plsk ²³⁷¹	NLVAQISALA	LQLDSEDLYS YTGSQLFEMH EK ²⁴⁰²	lgtm (610)
12925.1	-7.4	4.80	1097.6079	-0.0009	2/2	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGTMANSIIR ²⁴¹²	nlqs (1452)	
12936.1	-6.9	4.55	1097.6079	-0.0005	2/2	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGTMANSIIR ²⁴¹²	nlqs (1452)	
12739.1	-6.7	4.66	1097.6079	-0.0015	2/2	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGTMANSIIR ²⁴¹²	nlqs (1452)	
12730.1	-6.2	4.34	1097.6079	-0.0019	2/2	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGTMANSIIR ²⁴¹²	nlqs (1452)	
13553.1	-4.9	4.05	1113.6028	-0.0016	2/2	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGTMANSIIR ²⁴¹²	nlqs (1452)	
16489.1	-4.3	5.12	1081.6130	-0.0004	2/2	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGTMANSIIR ²⁴¹²	nlqs (1452)	
16500.1	-4.1	5.14	1081.6130	-0.0004	2/2	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGTMANSIIR ²⁴¹²	nlqs (1452)	
13547.1	-3.7	4.08	1113.6028	0.0010	2/2	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGTMANSIIR ²⁴¹²	nlqs (1452)	
18241.1	-2.3	4.54	1701.9467	-0.0017	3/3	mhek ²⁴⁰³	LGTMANSIIR	NLQSR ²⁴¹⁷	wrsp (22)
4581.1	-4.5	4.77	1089.5168	-0.0011	2/3	lqsr ²⁴¹⁸	WRSPAHENS ²⁴²⁶	(24)	
4593.1	-2.9	4.74	1089.5168	-0.0012	2/3	lqsr ²⁴¹⁸	WRSPAHENS ²⁴²⁶	(24)	

1. p.N2114T#-12.99525 rs27893940 | dbSNP | gpmdb |

Protein Information

If the information below appears incomplete, press: [go](#)

ENSEMBL Protein report: ENSMUSP00000064155

Description: This transcript is not in the current gene set. Previous versions of the protein may be available on the [Protein History page](#).

Protein Sequence:

Contributor: anonymous

store trace yes

Column notes.

1. **spectrum**: written in the form "X.Y", where X is a unique identifier for a particular tandem mass spectrum in this data set and Y is an identifier for this particular sequence solution.
2. **log(e)**: the base-10 log of the expectation that any particular peptide assignment was made at random (E-value).
3. **log(l)**: the base-10 log of the sum of the fragment ion intensities in the tandem mass spectrum used to make this assignment.
4. **m+h**: the calculated mass of the protonated parent ion for this sequence assignment.
5. **delta**: the difference between the measured and calculated protonated parent ion masses.
6. **ζ**: the ratio of the measured charge of the parent ion to the number of basic sites in the assigned peptide sequence.
7. **sequence**: the sequence of the assigned peptide sequence. The sequences immediately N-terminal and C-terminal to the assigned peptide in the protein sequence are also shown.
8. **n**: the number of observations of this peptide sequence in GPMDB.
9. **w**: the frequency of observation for this peptide in this protein (only available for some species).

